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Review Article

Emotional Intelligence Effects on Post Traumatic Stress Disorder

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ABSTRACT

The Aim Of Literature Review Emotional Intelligence Was To Evaluate And Discuss About Previous Research On Emotional Intelligence and also aware to people that how emotional Intelligence affect on PTSD. Emotional Intelligence affects on PTSD by correlating advertisement concept showing them a Positive thoughts by Visual things. Advertise Gave An Idea About The How Control Emotions And How Feels Good Using Emotions and Creates Positive Thoughts. Nowadays Emotionally Intelligence Is Important Factor Because Every People Connected On Social Media So No Proper Face To Face Communication And Lead Depression Due To Loneliness. When Happiness, Success Comes In Your Life Your Emotions Are Seen On Your Face In The Sense Of Smilly Face And Brightening Of Your Face. Emotional Intelligence Helps You Make Or Build Stronger Relationships, Succeed At School Colleges And Work Place And Achieve Your Career And Personal Goals. It Should Also Help You To Connect With Your Feelings, Turn Intention Into Action And Make Informed Decisions About What Matters Most To You.

INTRODUCTION

Emotions: -

It Is the Way Of Expressing Thoughts Into Feelings. Emotions Are Reactions That Human Beings Experience In Response To Events Or Situations. Emotions Are Reactions To Stimuli And Feelings Are What We Experience As A Result Of Emotions. All Emotions May Be Positive Or Negative. Postive Emotions - These Are Pleasant, Includes Happiness.

Negative Emotions - These Emotions Are Unpleasant, It Includes Sadness, Anger and Fear. Emotional Intelligence Involves Five Types Of Skills.

- Self-Awareness
- Self-Managing Emotions
- Motivation
- Empathy
- Social Intelligence Skills

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Types Of Emotions:-

- Happiness
- Sadness
- Fear
- Anger
- Surprise
- Hatefulness

1.Happiness -

Happiness Is Expressed By Smiling Or Speaking In Enthusiastic Tone Of Voice. It Is Pleasant Emotion And Satisfactory.

2.Sadness :- Sadness Can Be Expressed By Crying And Quit.

3.Fear :- Fear Comes With The Threat Of Harm, Either Physical, Emotional, Or Psychological,Real Or Imagined.

4.Anger:- Anger Is An Emotion Characterized By Something Or Someone Feel Has Deliberately Done Wrong.

5.Surprise:-

It Is The Feeling Caused By Something That Is Unexpected Or Unusual.

6.Hatensess :-

Way To Express In Rude Manner.¹

Emotional Intelligence:-

A Person's Success And Achievements Are Based On His Intelligence.

Emotional Intelligence Is The Ability To Understand, Manage And Balance Your Own Emotions In Positive Ways To Remove Stress And Communicate Effectively.

Emotional Intelligence Is Nothing But To Empathize With Others,Overcome Challenges And Defuse Conflict. Emotional Intelligence Also Known As Emotional Quotient.(EQ).

The Concept Of Emotional Intelligence Was Popularised In 1995 By Psychologist Daniel Goleman. He Wrote The Book Emotional Intelligence.

Emotional Intelligence Includes Understand The Feeling And Take Good Decisions On That.

It Is One Of The Way Of Being Smart.

Intelligence Quotient (IQ) Provide The Information About Accuracy Or Cleverness In Academic School, College But Emotional Quotient Gives The Smartness In Works May Be In College That How Emotionally We Are Strong. Emotional Intelligence Will Help You To Manage Stress In Your Final Exams In Academic.

Some Experts Have Suggested That Emotional Intelligence Is Better Than Intelligence Quotient. We Can't Create Emotional Intelligence By Reading Books Like How To Gain Emotional Intelligence .It Is By Birth Or By Continuing The Same Thing In Your Life.

Not Only Intelligence Quotient Enough To Successful In Your Life. Emotionally Strong Makes The People Successful Life By Avoiding Stress . Emotionally Strong Means Balance,Control And Manage The Stress.

Success Depends Upon 20 Percent Of Intelligence And 80 Percent On Emotional Intelligence.

In Research It Is Found That Individuals Who Have Lower Emotional Intelligence In Face With Life Stressful Situations, Would Have Lower Adaptation, And Consequently Affected More By Depression, Disappointment, And Other Negative Effects.⁹

Importance Of Emotional Intelligence:-

- Improve Leadership Qualities
- Good Communication
- Self Knowledge
- Self Control
- Reduce Stress

The First Step To Improving Or Developing Emotional Intelligence Is To Learn How To Manage Stress.If You Are Not Managing Your Stress Then It Can Leads To Different Health Problems Such That Increases Blood Pressure,Suppresses The Immune System, Increases The Risk Of Heart Attacks And Strokes If You Can't Control Your Emotions You Making Anxiety And Depression.

After The Knowing How To Manage Stress Then Try To Understand How To Decline The Stress.²

History: -

The Factors Comes Under ‘Emotional Intelligence’ Were First Discussed Under Social Intelligence. Emotional & Social Intelligence Is A Combination Of Three Factors – Awareness, Attunement And Adaptability. The Term ‘Social Intelligence’ Was First Introduced In 1909 John Dewey. After That Edward Thorndike Was Used The Term Social Intelligence In 1920. Then In 1940 David Wechsler Used The Term Social Intelligence. In 1975- Howard Gardner Publishes “The Shattered Mind Which Discussed On The Concept Of Multiple Intelligences”. In 1985- American Researcher Wayne Payne Completed The Study Under Title Study Of Emotions. He Covered The Points Relating To Fear, Pain And Desire Etc. Keith Beasley First Used The Term EQ In An Article Mensa Magazine In 1987. 1990 Year Is An Important Year For Emotional Intelligence When John Mayer And Peter Salovey Published Their Article In The Journal Imagination, Cognition And Personality. In 1995 Daniel Goleman Released A Book Emotional Intelligence Which Is Very Popular In The World. He Explains About "Why It Can Matter More Than IQ".

The Existing Literature Review Grouped Emotional Intelligence Into Two Models

A) Ability Model

B) Mixed Model

A) Ability Model Of Emotional Intelligence:

This Model Is The Combination Of Main Ideas Of Intellectual And Emotions In 1997. Mayer And Salovey Introduced Emotional Intelligence In Four Categories.

1. Perception
2. Identification
3. Appraisal
4. Expression

B) Mixed Models Of Emotional Intelligence:-

It Further Includes Two Models

- Bar-On Model
- Goleman's Model

Bar-On Model:-

It Is Well-Known Mixed Model Of Emotional Intelligence In 1997. It Was Based On Personality Characteristics Bar-On Model Is Made By The Five Components Such As Follows

A) Intra-Personal Skills:-

Such As Self-Awareness, Self Regulations

B) Inter-Personal Skills:-

Such As Empathy, Self Responsibility

C) Adaptability:- Such As Flexibility, Problem Solving, Reality Testing

D) Stress Management:- Such As Impulse Control

E) General Mood:- Such As Happiness, Sadness And Anxiety^{3,4}

Goleman Model Of Intelligence:-

By Working On And Increasing These Five Skills, You Can Become More Emotionally Intelligent And Increase Your Emotional Intelligence.

Five Components Of Emotional Intelligence:-

- Self-Awareness
- Self-Managing Emotions
- Motivation
- Empathy
- Social Skills

Self-Awareness:- This Is Person's Capability To Understand And Be Aware Of Their Feelings And Moods. Self-Awareness Helps A Person Keep An Eye On Their Thoughts And Emotions So They Can Better Understand Why They Feel Like. To Become Self-Aware You Need To Monitoring Emotions.¹⁰

How To Improve Self-Awareness:-

- Set Goals
- Pay Attention To Your Thoughts, Feelings And Emotions
- Learn New Things
- Meditation
- Daily Exercise

Self-Management Emotions: - When You Become Overly Stressed, Your Ability To Both Think Clearly And Accurately Was Inappropriate. When You Over Stressed You Loose Control. So Properly Manage The Stress And Careful Thinking Before Do The Action.¹¹

Motivation:- Motivation Helps To Achieve The Goals By Using Their Emotions.

By Communicating Properly, Clearly , Inspires And Influence To People.

Motivate Your Self Using Emotions To Complete Your Aims Or Objectives.¹²

Empathy: -The Ability To Understand How Others Are Feeling If That Same Thing Happens With Him.

Empathy Means Recognising Emotional State Of Others. How Empathy Will Build:-

1. Talk To New People's
2. Listen To Others People
3. Be Willing To Share Your Feel
4. Imagine You In Some One's Place¹³

Social Skills: -

In Professional Jobs-Managers More Benefits by Build Good Relationship with Employees.

Social Skills Includes Good Listening, Verbal Communication Skills, Nonverbal Communication Skills, Leadership.

By Using Emotions Students Teachers Interaction Increases Impacts The Good Behaviour.⁸

Relationship Management: - You Know That How To Maintain And Improve Good Relationships. While When You Are In Angry Emotion Never Be Rude With Colleagues. Always Speak Properly With Colleagues At School, College Or Workplace That Maintains Good Relationship.⁷

For Relationship Management Following Aspects Are Important: -

- Be Aware of How Effectively You Use Non-Verbal Communication: -
- Use Humor To Relieve Stress: -

- Learn To See Conflict As An Opportunity To Grow Closer To Others:-
- Always Be Confident While Speaking Don't Be Hesitate.⁵

Purpose: -

New Concept Is Advertisement Correlation With Emotional Quotient.

Advertisement: -

Advertisement Is Key Role In Emotional Intelligence. Due To Visualization Mindset Of People Will Be Change Because Advertisement Change The Emotions To Decline The Strees And Anxiety By Intertaining People's.

This Is The Positive Approach For Emotional Intelligence Because It Entertains The People. That What People Saw In Advertisement They Thinking Abouts That And Causes Stress.

For Example:-

If People Seen Love Story Movies Person Feels Love, Affection And Caring .Either People Have Mood To See Comedy Movies Then They Feels Humorous Nature.

ADVANTAGES: -

Allow To Display Positive Advertise On Advertisement Platform Such As Yoga And Meditation. When People Saw The Advertise Then Feels Good And Try To Do Meditation.

It Creates Awareness About Health.

(Fig.1) Advantage of Advertise to PTSD²⁶

DISADVANTAGES: -

Disadvantages Of Advertisement Using Emotion Is People Sometimes Follows the Bad Habbits of Actors. When Person Thought Who Is Ideal for Me Then He Behave Like That Ideal Person Either He Was a Good Person Or Bad Person.

(Fig.2) disadvantage of Advertise to PTSD²⁷

Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD):-

What Is Trauma? Trauma Is An Emotional Response To A Terrifying Event Like An Accident, Rape Or Natural Disaster.

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder PTSD:- Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) Is A Mental Illness That Disrupts Normal Physical Or Mental Functions , That Develops In Some People Who Have Experienced The Fearing, Scary, Shocking Or Dangerous Events. It Is Natural Emotions Or Feeling Of Afraid After The Traumatic Condition. Peoples Who Have PTSD May Feel Stressed Or Frightened But Actually They Are Not In Danger. Women's Are Affected More Than Men.

Those Peoples Suffering PTSD Can Have Insomnia, Nightmares, Flashbacks And A Lot Of Painful Or Unpleasant Emotions.

(Fig. 3) PTSD factor²⁸

Causes Of PTSD:-

Examples Of Events In Posttraumatic Stress Disorder Includes

- Wars
- Crimes
- Accidents
- Death Of A Loved One
- Harassment
- Abuse

- Natural Calamities:- Such Fires And Floods
- Terrorist Attacks
- Personal Assault¹⁴

Risk Factors:-

Risk Factors For Developing PTSD Include:

- Physical Pain Or Injury
- Previous Trauma Condition
- Previously Anxiety Or Depression

Sign And Symptoms:-

In Most Of The Cases, Symptoms Developing During First Month After Traumatic Events.

Some Common Signs And Symptoms Are There You Might Recognise . It Can Includes

- Avoiding Feelings Or Memories
- Flashbacks
- Nightmares
- Reliving Aspects of What Happened
- Alertness Or Feeling on Edge
- Physical Symptoms-

Along With an Emotional Symptoms, Trauma Can Cause Physical Symptoms Such as Sweating, Headaches, Fatigue, Physical Sensations Such as Pain, Sweating, Nausea Etc.

- Arousal And Reactivity Symptoms:

- Difficulty In Sleeping
- Irritation And Anger
- Feeling Tense And Anxiety
- Difficulty In Concentrating¹⁵

What Is Flashback?

Flashback Is Nothing But You Feel That Traumatic Events Happening Right Now But Actually It Was Already Happened Or It Will Never Happen.

You Seeing Complete or Partial Images Of What Happened In Traumatic Event.

What Do You Mean by Nightmares?

Nightmare Is Also Called Bad Dreams Nightmares Can Cause You to Feel Various Emotions Including:

- Anger
- Sadness
- Guilt

- Fear
- Anxiety

Treatment :-

Medication:-

Doctors Advice To Use Antidepressant Medications To Treat PTSD.

-To Control The Feelings Of Anxiety.¹⁶

- Mood Stabilizers
- Neurotransmitter serotonin Or Norepinephrine-Such As

- A)Fluoxetine
- B)Paroxetine
- C)Sertraline
- D)Venlafexine

- Psychological Therapies - Such As Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT)

The FDA Approved Only This Drug Paroxetine And Sertraline For Treating PTSD.

Medication Such As Prazosin Is An α_1 Antagonist Can Reduce Levels Of Norepinephrine In The Central Nervous System And Reducing Nightmares Related To PTSD.¹⁷

Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT):-

It Is Treatment Therapy For Mental Disorders. It Helps Patients Understand How Thoughts Affect Emotions And Behaviors.

(Fig. 4) Cognitive Behavioural Therapy²⁹

Example: - One Day A Man Was Forget To Say Bye To His Wife As He Daily Do That.

CBT Trainers Helps You To Try To Remove Negative Thoughts And Add Positive Thoughts In Person's Mind. The Above Cycle Repeated Several Times In Cognitive Behavioral Therapy Treatment. Cognitive Behavioral Therapy Used

To Treating Mental Health Disorders, Such As Depression, Anxiety Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD). Mental Health Disorders That May Be Improve With CBT Includes :-

- Depression
- Anxiety Disorders
- Phobias
- PTSD
- Sleep Disorders¹⁸

Relationship Between PTSD And Emotional Intelligence:-

Simple Meaning Of Emotional Intelligence Means Control Balance Or Manage Your Own Emotions To Remove Stress In Positive Way.

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder Is Mental Condition When Trauma Condition Develop People With PTSD Feels Stressed And Frightened. Emotions Are Directly Linked With Stress.

Certain Emotions Like Anger, Shame, And Anxiety Usually Comes From Stress, Which Refers To Harmful, Threatening, Or Challenging Conditions, Showing A Relationship Between Stress And Emotion.¹⁹ In Studies We Have Found That Positive Emotions Increase Your Ability To Manage Stress While Negative Emotions Can Lead To Stress. When We Study The Emotional Intelligence Then We Easily Eliminate Stress.

The First Step To Controlling Stress Is To Know The Symptoms Of Stress. Exercise Is An Effective In Stress.²⁰ There Is No Specific Treatment For Stress. In Treatment Of Stress Focuses On Changing The Situation. When We Control The Symptoms Then Stress Automatically Reduce.²¹

Actual Meaning Of Stress?

Stress Is A Feeling Of Emotional Or Physical Tense. It Can Come From Any Event Or Thought That Makes You Feel Nervous, Frustrated, Angry. When You Are In Stressfull Situation, Your Heartbeat Increases, You Breathe Faster Than Normal , Muscle Tense And Excessive Sweating. This Is Body's Response To Stress -Fight And Flight Condition ²²

Health Problems Related To Stress:-

- Depression
- PTSD
- Alzheimer's Disease

Too Much Stress Can Lead To Depression.

Stress May Cause Some Types Of Sleep Disorders Such As

- Insomnia
- Sleep Apnoea

Physical Symptoms Of Stress Include:

- Headache
- High Blood Pressure
- Aches And Pain
- Chest Pain
- Weak Immune System
- Muscle Tension
- Stomach Or Digestion Problem²³

Emotional Symptoms Of Stress Includes:-

- Depression
- Anxiety
- Sadness
- Panic Attack

How To Reduce Stress:-

- Increase Physical Activity:-

If You're Feeling Stressed Moving Your Body Means Daily Walking. Engaging Our Body In Physical Activity Helps Reduce Stress Levels And Improve Mood.

- Healthy Diet :-

Nutritional Diet Reduces Stress. Person With Empty Stomach Can't Create Positive Emotions. Beverages Like Alcohol Reduce Stress.

Meditation May Help To Boost Your Mood And Decrease Symptoms Of Stress.²⁴

- Laugh Therapy:-

When You Laugh More You Take More Oxygen . Laughter Also Improves Your Immune System,Pain And Improves Your Mood For Long Duration Of Time.

- Talk Therapy:-

Talk Therapy Used To Deal With Stress, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy,Talk Therapy

Helps In PTSD A Therapist Helps You To Change Negative Thoughts Into Positive Thoughts.

- Connect With People:-
Spend Time With Your Friends Or Family Members One Who Listens To You.
- Exercise-Daily Exercise
- Drinking Alcohol To Relieve Stress But Doesn't Work In The Long Term.
- Do Something That Makes You Happy Such Listening Song, Dancing Playing Game.²⁵

Observation For PTSD :

Graphical Table 1. Post Traumatic Stress Disorder Result: -

The Principle of Emotional Intelligence To Predict And Improve The Life Of Individual. By Controlling And Managing The Emotions We Live Better Life. Emotional Intelligence Affects Post Traumatic Stress Disorder by Showing Visual Things.

CONCLUSION: -

Emotional Intelligence effects on PTSD by correlating advertisement concept showing them a Positive thought by Visual things. Finally At the End Of Literature Review It Is Find That Emotional Intelligence Is Correlated With Concept Advertisement. Advertise Gave An Idea About The How Control Emotions And How Feels Good Using Emotions and Creates Positive Thoughts.^{6,7} Nowadays Emotionally Intelligence Is Important Factor Because Every People Connected On Social Media So No Proper Face To Face Communication And Lead Depression Due To Loneliness.

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